

Verifiability and Privacy in Federated Learning through Context-Hiding Multi-Key Homomorphic Authenticators

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Abstract

Federated Learning has rapidly expanded from its original inception to now have a large body of research, several frameworks, and sold in a variety of commercial offerings. Thus, its security and robustness is of significant importance. There are many algorithms that provide robustness in the case of malicious clients. However, the aggregator itself may behave maliciously, for example, by biasing the model or tampering with the weights to weaken the model's privacy. In this work, we introduce a verifiable federated learning protocol that enables clients to verify the correctness of the aggregator's computation without compromising the confidentiality of their updates. Our protocol uses a standard secure aggregation technique to protect individual model updates with a linearly homomorphic authenticator scheme that enables efficient, privacy-preserving verification of the aggregated result. Our construction ensures that clients can detect manipulation by the aggregator while maintaining low computational overhead. We demonstrate that our approach scales to large models, enabling verification over large neural networks with millions of parameters.

CCS Concepts

• **General and reference** → **Verification**; • **Security and privacy** → **Privacy-preserving protocols**; **Cryptography**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Client-server architectures**.

Keywords

Federated Learning, Malicious Aggregator Detection, Model Integrity Verification, Homomorphic Authenticators.

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1 Introduction

Current advancements in Generative AI are made possible because of large public datasets or in-house dataset curation by organizations working on such models. In several domains, including crucial sectors like finance and healthcare, it is not possible to accumulate such an overwhelming amount of data to train effective and accurate models. There are several reasons for this, most of which rely on the inherent confidentiality of the data needed to train such models.

Hence, alternative solutions have been explored to train AI models without directly sharing datasets. These techniques are generally grouped under the Trustworthy AI topic [19], which includes methods and techniques for training AI models in a secure, privacy-preserving, fair, and verifiable fashion.

In this context, Federated Learning (FL) is a well-established paradigm that allows entities, such as government organizations, companies, and hospitals, to collaboratively train a Machine Learning (ML) model in a distributed fashion without sharing their private plaintext data. With the help of FL, such entities, known as clients, collect and hold the data, train a local FL model, and share the updated model's parameters with each other or with a third-party entity called the aggregator. The aggregator then combines these individual contributions into a new global model. This process is repeated over several rounds to iteratively refine the global model. By the end of the training process, the clients will have a shared FL model trained on the combined data from all entities.

Although FL is advocated as a privacy-enhancing technology¹, in its default implementation has several possible attacks and security issues. For example, FL systems are vulnerable to inference attacks [12] where an attacker (such as a client or the aggregator) can infer sensitive information about other participants' private data from the ML algorithm parameters [13].

While there is a significant body of research around protecting FL systems against malicious clients [2], the aggregator remains a critical vulnerability. As the central entity responsible for collecting and aggregating clients' parameters, it can act dishonestly, which enables essentially arbitrary manipulation and tampering. The aggregator may bias the overall model towards unfair outcomes, disregard contributions by certain clients or user groups, or insert one or more backdoors into the model to control its predictions given targeted inputs [17]. This is in addition to the privacy concerns posed by a dishonest aggregator, where in addition to potentially launching privacy attacks against specific clients, it can tamper with the weights to make privacy attacks even easier with so-called "weight trap attacks" [3].

¹<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/privacy-enhancing-technologies/>

Thus, to combat these problems, verifying the aggregator’s behavior in FL has started to receive more attention. Existing works have proposed using schemes based on homomorphic hashes [8] or Paillier-based encryption [5]. However, shortfalls remain, either due to prohibitively long running times or lack of privacy protections.

In this work, we propose a novel FL protocol that ensures both privacy and verifiability of model aggregation. Our construction enables clients to verify that the aggregator has performed the computation correctly without revealing their private model updates in plaintext. This is achieved by combining a standard masking-based Secure Aggregation scheme, ensuring the confidentiality of individual updates, with a Context-Hiding Identity-Based Multi-Key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticators scheme that guarantees integrity and verifiability of the aggregation process.

Clients authenticate vectors of model parameters using the homomorphic authenticator, enabling the server to aggregate both masked updates and corresponding signatures efficiently. The homomorphic property allows each client to verify the correctness of the aggregated result without compromising clients privacy. We reduce computational and communication overhead by authenticating vectors instead of individual elements, ensuring practicality for large-scale FL deployments.

Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose a verifiable FL protocol that ensures both the privacy of client updates and the integrity of server aggregation;
- We integrate a linearly homomorphic authenticator scheme into a FL model to enable efficient and privacy-preserving verification of aggregated results;
- We implemented the protocol and we present experiments showing that our construction scales to FL models with millions of parameters. The implementation will be released as open source².

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes related works. Section 3 provides an overview of the cryptographic primitives used to ensure verifiability and privacy of model updates. Section 4 describes our protocol, outlining roles and interactions, and evaluates its security. Section 5 reports the experiments and results. Finally, Section 6 concludes and highlights future research directions.

2 Related Works

Federated Learning enables multiple parties to train ML models without sharing private data, where clients send updates to an aggregator that combines them into a global model. However, FL remains susceptible to inference attacks [12], where the aggregator may act maliciously by tampering with clients’ model weights.

To ensure privacy, techniques such as Secure Multi-party Computation (SMC) [14], Differential Privacy [16], and Homomorphic Encryption [18] have been employed. Yet, using these techniques individually is challenging, leading to hybrid approaches [5]. Despite progress, issues such as long execution times, reduced accuracy, and insufficient privacy remain.

Recent studies introduce trusted layers around FL models to reduce reliance on aggregators while ensuring correct computations. One of the most comprehensive works is RoFL [11], which secures aggregation with ElGamal commitments and validates inputs through Zero-Knowledge (ZK) proofs. While providing strong guarantees, it suffers from high computational costs and scalability challenges, as decoding aggregated updates requires solving discrete logarithms (feasible due to the constrained aggregation space, i.e., 32-bit integers). Similar results are obtained by LightVeriFL [6], ensuring verifiability with homomorphic hashes and Pedersen commitments, but increasing communication and coordination overhead.

Despite these efforts, there is still no comprehensive solution addressing aggregator attacks while remaining practical. Existing cryptographic mechanisms often add complexity or overhead, whereas our approach focuses on simplicity and scalability by combining standard secure aggregation with a lightweight authenticator scheme.

3 Preliminaries

In this section, we briefly present the basic primitives used in our construction.

3.1 Secure Aggregation

Several techniques guarantee input privacy in FL, such as Differential Privacy (adding noise to training parameters to hide individual contributions [10]) and masking-based secure aggregation (obfuscating updates so that masks cancel out during aggregation [4]). Our implementation adopts a modified version of the masking-based protocol by Bonawitz et al. [4], due to its efficiency and ability to protect individual updates without heavy cryptographic operations, while ensuring verifiability and integrity of the aggregated model.

This protocol consists of the following algorithms:

- *KeyGen*(\cdot): Each client u generates pairwise shared secrets with every other client v in the system using a secure key exchange protocol (e.g., Diffie-Hellman key exchange). The shared secret between clients u and v is denoted as $z_{u,v} = z_{v,u}$. These pairwise keys enable clients to generate correlated pseudorandom masks that will algebraically cancel during aggregation.
- *Mask*($x_u, \{z_{u,v}\}$): Given client u ’s local model update x_u and the set of pairwise shared secrets $\{z_{u,v}\}$, this algorithm computes a masked version of the update. Client u generates its pseudorandom mask as $r_u = \sum_{v \in S, v > u} PRG(k_{u,v}) - \sum_{v \in S, v < u} PRG(k_{u,v})$, where S is the set of active clients in the round and PRG is a pseudorandom function. The masked update is computed as $\tilde{x}_u = x_u + r_u$. This construction ensures that the pseudorandom components will sum to zero across all clients while individual updates remain hidden from the server.
- *Unmask*($\{\tilde{x}_u\}_{u \in S}$): This algorithm is executed by the server after collecting all masked updates from the client set S . The server computes the aggregate as $\sum_{u \in S} \tilde{x}_u = \sum_{u \in S} (x_u + r_u) = \sum_{u \in S} x_u + \sum_{u \in S} r_u$. By the construction of the pairwise masks, $\sum_{u \in S} r_u = 0$ since each pseudorandom value $PRF(k_{u,v})$ appears exactly twice in the sum with opposite

²Available here: <https://github.com/SimoneBottoni/verifiable-fl>.

signs (once positive for the client with smaller index, once negative for the client with larger index). Therefore, the server recovers the true aggregate $\sum_{u \in S} x_u$ without learning any individual client contribution.

The presented methods are simplified to illustrate their role in our protocol; for a detailed explanation, see [4].

3.2 Homomorphic Authenticators

Multi-Key Homomorphic Authenticator schemes enable multiple parties to sign and homomorphically aggregate data, producing a verifiable aggregate signature without revealing individual contributions. This is particularly useful in distributed computations requiring confidentiality. In the following, we use “sign” and “authenticate” interchangeably.

Our protocol adopts the Context-Hiding Identity-based Multi-Key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticator scheme by Schabhüser et al. [15], which offers properties suited to our construction: (i) Multi-Key Signatures: each participant owns a private key derived from their identity and can independently generate a partial authenticator for a message. These can be combined into a single valid signature for the aggregated result, without a shared key or trusted setup; (ii) Linearly Homomorphic: the scheme supports linear operations on authenticated data, so if signatures $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n$ correspond to messages m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n , the combined signature σ_{agg} authenticates $m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_n$; and (iii) Context-Hiding: ensures input privacy, preventing inference of individual contributions from the signatures.

This protocol consists of the following algorithms:

- *Setup*(1^λ): On input of a security parameter λ , this algorithm generates the system’s public parameters pp , which are published and used by all participants.
- *KeyGen*(pp, id): On input the public parameters pp and a unique identity $id \in \mathbb{N}$, this algorithm generates the identity-specific secret key sk_{id} and the corresponding verification key vk_{id} .
- *Auth*(sk_{id}, x_u): On input a secret key sk_{id} and a client u ’s vector of local model update $x_u \in \mathbb{R}^d$, where d is the length of the vector, this algorithm outputs an authenticator $\sigma_u = (\Lambda, R, S)$. Here, Λ contains identity-specific components that bind the signature to the signer’s identity, while R and S are global components that enable homomorphic operations across different signers’ authenticators.
- *Eval*($\sigma_u \in S$): On input a set of authenticators $\sigma_u \in S$, where S is the set of active clients in the round, this algorithm computes the homomorphic evaluation $\sigma_{agg} = \sum_{u \in S} \sigma_u$ authenticating the linear combination $x_{agg} = \sum_{u \in S} x_u$ without accessing individual updates x_u , preserving context-hiding.
- *Ver*($vk_{id} \in S, x_{agg}, \sigma_{agg}$): On input a set of verification keys corresponding to the identities involved in the computation, the aggregated update x_{agg} , and authenticator σ_{agg} , this algorithm outputs 1 iff σ_{agg} is a valid aggregated signature for x_{agg} under the specified identities. Verification confirms both the authenticity of contributions and the correctness of the homomorphic aggregation.

Figure 1: Overview of the protocol phases.

The presented methods are described in simplified form to illustrate their use in our protocol; for a complete description, refer to [15].

4 Verifiable Federated Learning

In this section, we present our construction that enables clients to securely train a global FL model while ensuring integrity and correctness of the aggregated parameters.

4.1 Construction

Our protocol requires an initialization phase conducted by a trusted entity. During this phase, the necessary cryptographic parameters are generated and made publicly available to all the involved parties. We assume that the trusted entity may safely go offline once this phase is complete.

Using the published public parameters, each client can independently generate a unique identity id and a key-pair consisting of a secret key and the corresponding verification key, as follows:

$$(sk_{id}, vk_{id}) = \text{KeyGen}(pp, id) \quad (1)$$

Additionally, we assume the existence of a public key infrastructure that allows clients to register their identities. Specifically, each client publishes its identity id and the corresponding verification key vk_{id} to a publicly accessible bulletin board [4, 7]. This mechanism prevents any adversary, such as the aggregator or external entities, from impersonating honest clients. To avoid the usage of a third-party public bulletin board and to reduce the risks associated with their potential compromise, solutions based on blockchain can be used as an alternative [9].

The system involves the active collaboration of multiple parties, as shown in Figure 1. Two of them concretely contribute to the computation of the global FL model: the aggregator and a variable number of clients. The clients train the global FL model by computing model parameters locally, authenticating, and masking them. Once done, they request the aggregator to perform the necessary operations to obtain the final global FL model. Optionally, clients may verify the resulting model’s correctness to ensure the protocol has been followed accurately and without tampering. The aggregator’s primary role is to aggregate the clients’ weights and authenticators, then return the results to the clients. It can be honest but curious, attempting to infer information from the clients’ parameters, or malicious, trying to undermine the protocol’s integrity.

Our protocol is structured into different phases, executed identically in each round except for the initialization phase, which occurs beforehand. For simplicity, we describe a single round, assuming all parties perform identical operations in each iteration.

The initialization phase, as previously mentioned, takes place before the protocol execution and is performed only once.

Each round of the protocol starts with the Training Phase, during which each client k trains its local FL model on private data and obtains a matrix of model updates $X^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot m}$, where d is the number of rows and m is the number of columns. It is assumed that each client generates a fixed number of model updates in every round.

To maintain simplicity in notation and clarity in protocol flow, we adopt the following notational conventions. We use $x_{ij}^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot m}$ to denote a single value, corresponding to the i -th element of the j -th column of the model update matrix $X^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot m}$. Similarly, we use $x_j^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ to denote the j -th column of $X^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot m}$. This notation will remain consistent throughout the rest of the description.

In the Client Preparation Phase, each client prepares its local model updates for secure and verifiable aggregation. This phase ensures both the privacy of individual model updates and the integrity of the global aggregation. Each client performs two key operations on its model update matrix $X^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \cdot m}$. First, to protect the confidentiality of individual updates, the client masks each element of the matrix using a masking-based Secure Aggregation scheme, as described in Section 3.1. Specifically, for each element $x_{i,j}^{(k)}$ the client computes:

$$c_{i,j}^{(k)} = \text{Mask}(x_{i,j}^{(k)}, \{z_{u,v}\}) \quad (2)$$

where $\{z_{u,v}\}$ denotes the shared random values used in the masking procedure. This ensures that the server learns only the aggregated result and cannot infer any individual client’s data. Second, to enable post-aggregation verification, the client generates an authenticator for each column $x_j^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ of its model update matrix using the homomorphic signature scheme presented in Section 3.2. The authenticator is computed as:

$$\sigma_j^{(k)} = \text{Auth}(sk_{id}, x_j^{(k)}) \quad (3)$$

where sk_{id} is the private key of the client. This authenticator allows any verifier to later check that the client’s contribution has been correctly included in the final aggregate. Clients authenticate vectors rather than individual values in order to minimize

communication and computational overhead. This optimization increases efficiency while maintaining security guarantees. Finally, each client transmits both the masked model update vectors and their corresponding authenticators to the aggregator for secure aggregation and subsequent verification.

The second phase of the protocol is the Aggregation Phase, during which the aggregator processes the masked model updates and authenticators received from all participating clients in order to compute the global model updates. Specifically, the aggregator performs the following operations:

$$x_{i,j} = \text{UnMask}(\{c_{i,j}^{(k)}\}_{k \in S}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_j = \text{Eval}(\{\sigma_j^{(k)}\}_{k \in S}) \quad (5)$$

where S denotes the set of active clients in the current round. The first operation reconstructs the aggregated model update for the (i, j) -th entry by removing the masking applied during the Secure Aggregation phase. The second operation aggregates the individual authenticators $\sigma_j^{(k)}$ provided by the clients into a single authenticator σ_j , using the homomorphic properties of the underlying signature scheme.

The final phase of the protocol is the Client Verification Phase, in which each client (optionally) verifies the correctness of the aggregation performed by the aggregator. The aggregator broadcasts the aggregated model updates and the corresponding aggregate authenticator to all clients. Upon receiving this information, each client performs a verification step to ensure that the aggregation has been carried out honestly and without manipulation. Each client computes the following:

$$\text{check}_j = \text{Ver}(\{vk_{id}\}_{id \in S}, x_j, \sigma_j) \quad (6)$$

where $\{vk_{id}\}_{id \in S}$ are the public verification keys of the participating clients in the set S , x_j is the aggregated update vector for column j , and σ_j is the corresponding aggregate authenticator. The function Ver denotes the verification algorithm associated with the employed homomorphic signature scheme. If the verification succeeds, the client accepts the result and proceeds to compute the final average by dividing each aggregated value by the number of participating clients:

$$x_{i,j} = x_{i,j}/|S| \quad (7)$$

Subsequently, the client updates its model and proceeds to the next training round. However, if the verification fails for any column, it indicates potential misbehavior by the aggregator, such as incorrect or malicious computation. In such cases, the client rejects the aggregation result, and the round is considered invalid.

4.2 Security Consideration

Our protocol ensures two key properties in FL: privacy of client updates and verifiability of aggregation. Client privacy is guaranteed by the secure aggregation scheme, which masks updates to prevent the server or unauthorized parties from accessing raw data. Aggregation integrity is ensured through Context-Hiding Identity-based Multi-Key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticators, allowing clients to independently verify correctness. We analyze security under two adversarial models:

Semi-honest aggregator. In the semi-honest model, the aggregator follows the protocol but may attempt to infer private information from the data it receives. Masking prevents this by obfuscating each client’s updates before transmission, so the aggregator operates only on masked values. Even passive analysis or inference attacks cannot reveal the original contributions, ensuring that individual updates remain confidential throughout aggregation.

Malicious aggregator. A malicious aggregator may attempt to learn sensitive data or actively tamper with the protocol, including modifying updates, injecting values, or incorrectly aggregating data and signatures. Each client authenticates its updates using its private key, and the aggregator performs aggregation over masked values and authenticators. Due to the homomorphic property, any unauthorized modification – for example, altering the aggregated vector x_{agg} or injecting a malicious value e so that $x'_{agg} = x_{agg} + e$ or $x'_{agg} = e$ – invalidates the resulting signature. Attempts to forge aggregated authenticators, such as introducing a forged signature σ_e and computing $\sigma'_{agg} = Eval(\{\sigma_j^{(k)}\}_{k \in S} \cup \sigma_e)$, are also detectable. Clients verify the final result using public verification keys $\{vk_{id}\}_{id \in S}$ published before aggregation, so any deviation from valid keys results in verification failure. Compromised rounds are discarded, preventing undetected manipulation of the global model.

Formal security proofs for masking-based Secure Aggregation and the Context-Hiding Identity-based Multi-Key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticators scheme can be found in [4, 15].

5 Experimental Evaluation

We now present the implementation details of our construction and the experimental configuration used to evaluate its performance. We then describe the evaluation methodology and report results obtained by testing our protocol with a few million model updates.

Experimental Setup. Our protocol is implemented in the Rust programming language, utilizing the Arkworks library [1] for efficient cryptographic operations. Specifically, we employ the BLS12-381 pairing-friendly elliptic curve through the ark-bls12-381 module. All experiments were conducted on a multi-threaded setting on a commodity laptop: a MacBook Pro powered by 11 cores and 36 GB of RAM.

5.1 Federated Learning Accuracy

The common requirement in cryptography that floating point numbers must be truncated to a fixed precision for later encoding into an integer format results in a twofold influence on the protocol: the lower the handled precision results in faster commitment computation but can cause regular FL accuracy to drop.

We analyze the effect on performance on different datasets (we omit the results due to constraint space), and we discover that four decimal places of precision are sufficient for identical performance to running FL without the protocol, and hence maintaining full floating point precision. This level of precision is the one we use in the following cryptographic time evaluation experiments.

5.2 Cryptographic Time Evaluation

Cryptographic operations over large neural networks can introduce significant computational overhead. To assess the efficiency of our verification protocol, we measure the execution time of key cryptographic operations: (i) authenticator generation by clients, (ii) authenticator aggregation by the server, and (iii) verification of the aggregated authenticator by clients. We focus on these components as they dominate the cost of our verifiability mechanism and impact practical deployment. Since the underlying secure aggregation scheme for client privacy is well established and extensively studied, we omit its benchmarks. Our results thus highlight the additional overhead introduced by the authenticator scheme for integrity and verifiability.

Client’s Computation. In this phase, each client generates an authenticator over its model parameters using the Context-Hiding Identity-based Multi-Key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticator scheme before sending them to the aggregator. This ensures that clients can later verify the integrity of the aggregated result without revealing their private updates. Although this step adds computational overhead compared to standard FL, it remains efficient in practice. Our experiments show that generating authenticators for a model with one million parameters takes on average 2.8 seconds per client (see Figure 2). The authenticator scheme operates on vectors rather than individual values, allowing clients to batch parameters and reduce cryptographic operations. This design enhances parallelism: each column of the model update can be split into sub-columns (agreed upon by all clients) and processed independently. Thus, clients can better exploit multi-core architectures for concurrent computation, with the number of columns tuned to system capabilities (e.g., available CPU cores) to improve performance.

Aggregation. After clients submit their masked model updates and authenticators, the aggregator performs aggregation on both. Thanks to the homomorphic properties of the authenticator scheme, individual authenticators can be combined into a single aggregated authenticator matching the aggregate of clients’ updates. Our experiments show that the aggregation cost scales with the number of clients per FL round: about 2 ms for 100 clients, 6 ms for 500, and 15 ms for 1000 (see Figure 2). These results confirm that our protocol remains computationally efficient as the number of clients grows.

Client’s Verification. After receiving the aggregated model update and authenticator, each client verifies the correctness of the aggregator’s computation. This step is crucial to detect any malicious manipulation by the aggregator. On average, our results show that verifying the aggregated authenticator for a model with one million parameters takes about 10 milliseconds per client (see Figure 2).

5.3 Communication Overhead

Our protocol introduces some communication overhead compared to standard FL, as each client sends masked model updates along with a set of authenticators (one per column). The server returns the aggregated model and the corresponding aggregated authenticators. Since the number of columns is usually small, the additional communication cost remains limited.

Figure 2: Computation overhead in the protocol phases.

Client-to-Server Communication. Each client sends authenticators corresponding to their model updates to the server. The update vector is composed of m columns of size d , resulting in each client transmitting m authenticators — one per column. The size of each authenticator is constant and does not depend on the column length d , thus the overall communication overhead grows linearly with the number of columns m . As an example, a client sending authenticators for a model with 1 million parameters results in approximately 0.28 KB per authenticator transmitted.

Server-to-Client Communication. The server returns the aggregated masked model update, which has the same size as a single client's update, along with a single aggregated authenticator. This minimizes the communication overhead since the transmitted data does not scale with the number of participants.

6 Conclusion

We have introduced a novel verifiable federated learning protocol that guarantees the integrity of the aggregator's computations while preserving client privacy. Our experimental evaluation demonstrates that the overhead the authenticator scheme introduces is small. For a model with one million parameters, client authenticator generation takes approximately 2.8 seconds while the verification process takes approximately 10 milliseconds. Aggregation on the server requires around 15 milliseconds to aggregate authenticators from 1000 clients. Furthermore, our construction can be extended to handle dropout clients, enhancing its robustness and applicability in practical FL deployments.

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References

- [1] arkworks contributors. 2022. arkworks zkSNARK ecosystem. <https://arkworks.rs>
- [2] Peva Blanchard, El Mahdi El Mhamdi, Rachid Guerraoui, and Julien Stainer. 2017. Machine Learning with Adversaries: Byzantine Tolerant Gradient Descent. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2017, December 4-9, 2017, Long Beach, CA, USA*. 119–129.
- [3] Franziska Boenisch, Adam Dzedzic, Roei Schuster, Ali Shahin Shamsabadi, Ilya Shumailov, and Nicolas Papernot. 2023. When the Curious Abandon Honesty: Federated Learning Is Not Private. In *8th IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy, EuroS&P 2023, Delft, Netherlands, July 3-7, 2023*. IEEE, 175–199.
- [4] Kallista A. Bonawitz, Vladimir Ivanov, Ben Kreuter, Antonio Marcedone, H. Brendan McMahan, Sarvar Patel, Daniel Ramage, Aaron Segal, and Karn Seth. 2017. Practical Secure Aggregation for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS 2017, Dallas, TX, USA, October 30 - November 03, 2017*. ACM, 1175–1191.
- [5] Simone Bottoni, Stefano Braghin, Theodora S. Brisimi, and Alberto Trombetta. 2021. Privacy-Preserving Distributed Support Vector Machines. In *Heterogeneous Data Management, Polystores, and Analytics for Healthcare - VLDB Workshops, Poly 2021 and DMAH 2021, Virtual Event, August 20, 2021, Revised Selected Papers (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 12921)*. Springer, 85–102.
- [6] Baturalp Buyukates, Jinhyun So, Hessam Mahdavi, and Salman Avestimehr. 2024. LightVeriFL: A Lightweight and Verifiable Secure Aggregation for Federated Learning. *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Inf. Theory* 5 (2024), 285–301.
- [7] Amrita Roy Chowdhury, Chuan Guo, Somesh Jha, and Laurens van der Maaten. 2022. EIFFeL: Ensuring Integrity for Federated Learning. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS 2022, Los Angeles, CA, USA, November 7-11, 2022*. ACM, 2535–2549.
- [8] Dario Fiore, Rosario Gennaro, and Valerio Pastro. 2014. Efficiently Verifiable Computation on Encrypted Data. In *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, Scottsdale, AZ, USA, November 3-7, 2014*. ACM, 844–855.
- [9] Bowen Liu and Qiang Tang. 2024. Secure Data Sharing in Federated Learning through Blockchain-Based Aggregation. *Future Internet* 16, 4 (2024), 133.
- [10] Yunlong Lu, Xiaohong Huang, Yueyue Dai, Sabita Maharjan, and Yan Zhang. 2020. Differentially Private Asynchronous Federated Learning for Mobile Edge Computing in Urban Informatics. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informatics* 16, 3 (2020), 2134–2143.
- [11] Hidde Lycklama, Lukas Burkhalter, Alexander Viand, Nicolas Küchler, and Anwar Hithnawi. 2023. RoFL: Robustness of Secure Federated Learning. In *44th IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, SP 2023, San Francisco, CA, USA, May 21-25, 2023*. IEEE, 453–476.
- [12] Lingjuan Lyu, Han Yu, Xingjun Ma, Chen Chen, Lichao Sun, Jun Zhao, Qiang Yang, and Philip S. Yu. 2024. Privacy and Robustness in Federated Learning: Attacks and Defenses. *IEEE Trans. Neural Networks Learn. Syst.* 35, 7 (2024), 8726–8746.
- [13] Luca Melis, Congzheng Song, Emiliano De Cristofaro, and Vitaly Shmatikov. 2019. Exploiting Unintended Feature Leakage in Collaborative Learning. In *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, SP 2019, San Francisco, CA, USA, May 19-23, 2019*. IEEE, 691–706.
- [14] Payman Mohassel and Yupeng Zhang. 2017. SecureML: A System for Scalable Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning. In *2017 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy, SP 2017, San Jose, CA, USA, May 22-26, 2017*. IEEE Computer Society, 19–38.
- [15] Lucas Schabbüser, Denis Butin, and Johannes Buchmann. 2019. Context Hiding Multi-key Linearly Homomorphic Authenticators. In *Topics in Cryptology - CT-RSA 2019 - The Cryptographers' Track at the RSA Conference 2019, San Francisco, CA, USA, March 4-8, 2019, Proceedings (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 11405)*. Springer, 493–513.
- [16] Stacey Truex, Ling Liu, Ka Ho Chow, Mehmet Emre Gursoy, and Wenqi Wei. 2020. LDP-Fed: federated learning with local differential privacy. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Edge Systems, Analytics and Networking, EdgeSys@EuroSys 2020, Heraklion, Greece, April 27, 2020*. ACM, 61–66.
- [17] Chulin Xie, Keli Huang, Pin-Yu Chen, and Bo Li. 2020. DBA: Distributed Backdoor Attacks against Federated Learning. In *8th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2020, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, April 26-30, 2020*. OpenReview.net.
- [18] Chengliang Zhang, Suyi Li, Junzhe Xia, Wei Wang, Feng Yan, and Yang Liu. 2020. BatchCrypt: Efficient Homomorphic Encryption for Cross-Silo Federated Learning. In *Proceedings of the 2020 USENIX Annual Technical Conference, USENIX ATC 2020, July 15-17, 2020*. USENIX Association, 493–506.
- [19] Yue Zheng, Chip-Hong Chang, Shih-Hsu Huang, Pin-Yu Chen, and Stjepan Picek. 2024. An Overview of Trustworthy AI: Advances in IP Protection, Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning, Security Verification, and GAI Safety Alignment. *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Topics Circuits Syst.* 14, 4 (2024), 582–607.